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HYGIENIC ASSESSMENT OF THE WORKING CONDITIONS OF THE EMPLOYEES OF MODERN LIVESTOCK COMPLEXES

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Abstract:

In terms of the total injury rate (mild, severe and fatal injuries) of workers engaged in Q agricultural activities, among other types of economic activity, workers of livestock complexes and farms are consistently in the first place. Most of the accidents are accompanied by serious consequences. For the past 10 years in various agro-industrial complexes As a result of non-compliance of working conditions and safety standards, hazardous factors often lead to accidents of various degrees. Harmful factors are the cause of various work-related diseases. Workers in livestock complexes are no exception. Machine milking operators are the most common occupation in the dairy industry.

Key words : *work conditions, machine milking operator, milking equipment, cows milking*

ГИГИЕНИЧЕСКАЯ ОЦЕНКА УСЛОВИЙ ТРУДА РАБОТНИКОВ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ЖИВОТНОВОДЧЕСКИХ КОМПЛЕКСОВ

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Аннотация:

По общему травматизму (легкому, тяжелому и смертельному) работников, занятых в сельскохозяйственной деятельности, среди других видов экономической деятельности стабильно занимают первое место

работники животноводческих комплексов и ферм. Большинство аварий сопровождаются тяжелыми последствиями. В течение последних 10 лет в различных агропромышленных комплексах в результате несоблюдения условий труда и норм безопасности опасные факторы часто приводят к авариям различной степени тяжести. Вредные факторы являются причиной различных профессиональных заболеваний. Работники животноводческих комплексов не являются исключением. Операторы машинного доения — самая распространенная профессия в молочной отрасли.

Ключевые слова: условия труда, оператор машинного доения, доильное оборудование, дойные коровы.

Research purpose : animal husbandry workers working in complexes work conditions hygienic assessment.

Results of scientific work : Milking cows is one of the most difficult and time-consuming tasks in livestock complexes. Cows milking for depending on the adopted technology, this operation is from 40 to 60% of all labor costs. Milking equipment is installed both in stalls and in special milking rooms. In this regard, the working conditions of machine milking operators are changing. In one case, milking machine operators are in contact with the animals the whole time, performing many different actions (squeezing between animals to connect the machine, lifting milking pails). In other cases, milking in stalls is done with the help of mobile machines. It should be noted that the arrangement of the workplace during milking in stalls with portable milking machines is mainly subject to the zootechnical requirements of keeping animals and does not create good conditions for the normal operation of machine milking operators[7,6].

Here, a serious disadvantage in workplace planning is the expansion of the work volume and the unfavorable working conditions of the milking machine operators.

Thus, while preparing the udder for milking, hanging and removing the milking machines, the machine milking operator is repeatedly forced to crouch or bend down.

Timekeeping observations have shown that a machine milking operator has to bend down more than 150 times per shift . In addition, during milking, the operator is in the dangerous "animal contact" zone, stepping on the cow's leg, hitting the face with the cow's tail, hitting horns, fences and other factors that can lead to an accident[1,7].

It can be achieved in special milking rooms to reduce operations related to operator movement, create comfortable working conditions and reduce the time spent in the danger zone. When studying working conditions in milking parlors, it was found that the distance from the udder of one cow to the udder next to it is 0.9 m when cows are milked in a "Balyos" type milking machine, and when cows are milked in a "Tandem" machine. milking machine, it is 2.6 - 2.8 m. Therefore, it is more convenient to work on "Herringbone" type devices. In the tandem type milking machine, when connecting the tools and massaging the udder, the milking operator must lean over the edge of the ditch, so this operation creates inconvenience and increases the operator's stay in the danger zone[12,13].

Tables 1.1, 1.2 show timekeeping observations of machine milking operators during milking of one cow on different milking machines.

Table 1.1 - Time of the operator staying in the danger zone during milking on the Herringbone milking machine in the milking parlor

Manual labor	Time for milking (min.).
Preparing the udder for milking	0.45
Connection devices	0.30
Massage and machine milking Extinguishers	0.41
Total:	0.12
	1.28

Table 1.2 - Milking time of the machine milking operator in the danger zone
(ADM milking machine -)

Manual labor	Milking time per cow (min).
Preparing the cow for milking, washing and wiping her udder, milking the first flow of milk,	1.0
starting the machine	0.8
turn off the machine	0.3
turn off the device	0.85
Lubricating the cow's teats with a disinfectant solution	0, 64
Total for manual techniques	0.15
	0.1
	0.32
	4.16

Apart from the scheduled time, the machine milking operator is in contact with the animals during the entire shift.

As can be seen from the tables, the presence of the machine milking operator in the danger zone during milking in stalls is three times more than in the Elochka milking machine[1,8,12].

The disadvantage of the working conditions when milking cows with mobile machines or milk lines is that the machine milking operator makes many movements, which makes him very tired during the working day. He lifts the machines from cow to cow, connects and disconnects them, he has to bend and squat at least three times.

The most common workplace injuries are machine milking operators who are busy driving cows to the milking platform. Here, dangerous situations also arise in

the formation of the flow of cows for milking, which is provided for in the technology. Such cases often occurred during the operation of the Carousel milking plant, in front of which a large number of animals were gathered[2,5].

With partial automation of finished technological operations and full automation of final operations, the load factor of the machine milking operator should not exceed 0.45 - 0.55. Large values of this coefficient are inevitable due to excessive exposure of machines and devices in the udder or delay of the milking operator in performing preparatory work and controlling the movement of cows from the preparation machine.

In particular, there are requirements for the milking machine, which should be convenient in production and maintenance, reliable in operation, and not require manual adjustment during the milking process. The milking machine should be simple and easy to disassemble and assemble by hand, and should be easy to wash and clean.

Analysis of static materials on injuries shows that livestock accidents account for 40-50% of all cases in agriculture. The injury rate is particularly high in dairy farming.

At the same time, the actual situation of injuries shows that there are many unresolved issues regarding the safety of machine milking operators in milking parlors. A large group of dangerous factors have been identified in the workplaces of machine milking operators, among which the most dangerous are slippery floors and the impact of animals with their hind, front legs or tail[12,13].

When studies were conducted on the ergonomic indicators of working conditions at the workplaces of machine milking operators, a direct relationship between the incidence of morbidity and the ergonomic levels of workplaces was determined. One of the main causes of diseases of machine milking operators is poor working conditions. In order to determine the compliance of the type of equipment with ergonomic requirements, a classification of machine milking operators

according to the physical load from workplace controls and ease of working conditions was developed.

An analysis of the classification of workplaces according to the comfort of standing shows that 99.9% of machine milking operators work in an uncomfortable position, compared to 25% . Such working conditions are classified as severe under this criterion, with 0.1 percent of milking machine operators working in satisfactory conditions for 10 - 25 percent of the work shift.

Conclusion: It was found that the workers of livestock complexes were exposed to the combined effects of being in an uncomfortable working position and being in dangerous conditions in the zone of contact with animals . A direct correlation was found between the state of the disease and the level of ergonomics of workplaces. One of the main causes of diseases of machine milking operators is poor working conditions.

The profession of a machine milking operator is one of the most traumatic professions, and the problem of improving working conditions and reducing the rate of industrial injuries and occupational diseases is very urgent.

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